

REFLECTIONS ON HEGELIAN ETHICAL DOCTRINE OF STATE: ISSUES IN POLITICAL THEORY

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Abstract

This article examines the Ethical Doctrine of State often referred to as the Dialectical Theory of State associated with the name of G.W.F Hegel, one of the greatest and perhaps most difficult political theorists of the State in Western intellectual tradition. Against the backdrop of other theories of State within the philosophical system of ideas such as the organic theories of the classical era of Plato and Aristotle and the social contract theories of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau, the paper argued that his dialectical theory of State despite its pitfalls was an improvement on the Philosophical ideas on the State and its central role of distributing justice in the society.

Keywords: *Ethical doctrine, Dialectics, Theory, State*

Introduction

Political theory attempts to explore the intellectual content of the processes of resolving the conflicts that arise among human beings in their effort to live together within a political and economic arrangement in order that a certain minimum of justice for each member of the social group is assured. Thus, the distribution of justice becomes the primary purpose of the state, an understanding of which, challenges our understanding of the theory of State.

This article examines the Dialectical Theory of State associated with the name of G.W.F Hegel, one of the greatest and perhaps most difficult political theorists of the State in Western intellectual tradition. Against the backdrop of other theories of State within the philosophical system of ideas such as the organic theories of the classical era of Plato and

Aristotle and the social contract theories Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau, the paper argued that his dialectical theory of State despite its pitfalls was an improvement on the Philosophical ideas on the State and its central role of distributing justice in the society.

On the Concept of State

Many writers have tried to define the State in various ways. Indeed, there are many definitions of the State, as there are scholars. Held (1980) for example explains that;

The state or apparatus of government appears to be everywhere, regulating the condition of our lives from birth registration to death certification. Yet, the nature of the state is hard to grasp. This may seem peculiar in case of something very pervasive in private and public life, but it is specifically this pervasiveness, which makes it difficult to understand. There is not anything so central to political and social theory as the nature of the state, and nothing more contested (p.11).

In a similar vein, Laski (1981) points out that the State for us remains both important and pervasive. According to him, the state is the crowning point of the modern social edifice, and it is in its supremacy over all other forms of social groupings that its special nature is to be found. This is how he puts it:

Within the confines of its territory, whatever it decides is binding upon all residents within that territory. They may consider its decisions immoral or unwise; they are nevertheless legally bound to obey them.... The power of the State is not exerted in vacuum. It is used to achieve certain ends, and its rules are, in their substance, altered to secure the ends deemed good at some particular time by those in possession of the legal right to operate its powers (p.11).

The pervasive nature of the State has also been buttressed by other scholars such as Miliband (1969) who argues that “the State is not a thing, it does not exist. What the State stands for is a number of particular institutions, which together constitutes its reality, and interact as parts of what may be called State system” (p.49).

Now, inspite of these explanations by scholars on the idea and nature of the State it may be said that there exist basically, two schools of thought on the State. These are namely, the liberal or bourgeois and the Marxist or radical schools of thought.

In Liberal or bourgeois political thought, the State is seen as an abstract entity, a moral and collective body, which is created by general agreement of the whole community. It is seen as a neutral body which is impartial towards all in its fold. Its primary duty is to balance things and maintain law and order for the benefits of all within it. As Ekekwe (1985) observes:

The Liberal view is that the state is neutral that it merely balances things out between competing elite groups. According to this view, there is no ruling class as such in society; therefore state power is not exercised in faovur of any such class” (p.10).

In the views of some Scholars, this conception of the neutrality of the State and the extolling of the rule of law conceals the true nature of the bourgeois State. It belies its class and economic base, and is unscientific. Miliband (1969) for instance, notes that this view of the State especially with regards to the countries of advanced capitalism is in all basics wrong; that this is viewed as very far from providing a guide to reality constitutes a thoughtful obfuscation of it. He suggests that an alternative concept of the State may be found in Marxist school of thought. In this regard, Amin (1983) notes that:

... the scientific theory of the evolution of societies teaches us that the state only appears where class antagonisms exist, for the state is only the instrument by which one class dominates another (p.125).

This class character of the State has been recognized by such liberal scholars as Adam Smith when he noted that:

Till there be belongings there can not be a government, the extreme end of which is to secure wealth and to defend the rich from the poor. (Smith, 1956, p.152).

However, Marx and Engels have in their *Communist Manifesto* provided the Philosophical and intellectual foundation for Marxist political Thought and from which the Marxist or radical concept of the state can be derived. In the *Manifesto*, Marx and Engels sought both to

popularize the mode of analysis (i.e. historical and dialectical materialism) and a political programme based on this analytical approach. For Marx and Engels (1996);

Each step in the development of the bourgeoisie was accompanied by a corresponding political advance of that class... since the establishment of the modern industry and of the world market, conquered for itself, in the modern representative state, exclusively, political sway. The executive of the modern state is but a committee for managing the common affairs of the whole bourgeoisie.

In this sense, the State from a materialist perspective is the instrument of domination of the bourgeoisie, and it necessarily follows that the state is an essential means of class domination in capitalist society. The State arises not only in the midst of class conflict, but also within the context of addressing and solving class conflict, and thus turns out to be undertaken in the interest of the dominant class. Lenin (1965) puts it aptly;

The State is the product and manifestation of the irreconcilability of class antagonisms. The state arises where and when to such extent that class antagonisms without prejudice cannot be submissive. And conversely the existence of the state proves that class antagonisms are irreconcilable (p.9).

Thus, contrary to bourgeois mystification, the State is an instrument of class dominance and control for property accumulation. Here, the state is viewed as maintaining an order in which the interests of the ruling class are favoured in the long run. This is because it preserves the conditions under which the ruling (bourgeois) class is dominant.

It has often been said that the state has not always existed. This is because it is possible to go into a time when there was no State. Historically, the State developed out of irreconcilable and antagonistic social interests and forces in the process of production, exchange and accumulation. This means that as the forces and actors of production developed in society, the structures and institutions of the State became gradually established. What this means by implication is that, the more developed the factors of production or the productive forces of society, the more developed the State becomes; and inversely, the less developed the productive forces of society, the less developed the state structures become. Hence, it has been observed that in advanced capitalist world there exists strong state structures while the

less developed countries of the Third World especially in Africa, are characterized by very weak and less developed state structure.

Thus, it can be safely said that the State not only transcends the idea of government and its machineries but actually reflects the degree of solidity and constitution of the factors and forces of production of any society; and its nature (i.e. the nature of the State) is determined by the totality of authority over the factors of production such as land, labour and capital. Infact, the understanding of the structures, nature and composition of the complex relationships between labour and capital is fundamental in the understanding of the state at any historical epoch in time. This is so because political authority is created through the interactions of the factors of production through the process of accumulation. Thus, the State can be defined as a complex, dynamic, volatile and sometimes, unpredictable interaction of network of interests, contradictions, institutions and processes which interact at varying levels for the reproduction of a particular social formation at any particular point in time.

Right from the classical period of Greek City- States built by slave labour to the medieval period of Church – State controversy which dove – tailed to the period of Renaissance with the rise of the nation – state which crystallized in the modern capitalist state in which labour is dominated and oppressed, the state has become the single most powerful force in society. Either in its overt and/or covert manifestations, the state has come to dominate and regulate not only the processes of production, exchange and consumption, but also, the entire spectrum of social and political life. The State determines the ideological direction of society and dictates the nature of political relations as well as the mode of interactions with external interests. Therefore, it is pertinent to take into cognizance, the following factors in the discussion of the idea of State in any society.

1. The degree of the development of the productive forces of the society;
2. The extent of commodification in the social formation;
3. The structure of power and production, whether of use or exchange value;
4. The historical development of institutions, structures and relations;

5. The degree of solidity and composition of the contending forces, the nature, composition and direction of class contradictions and struggles, and finally,
6. The general pattern and structure of systemic reproduction in the society.

It is in the consideration of the above factors that Hegel developed his dialectical theory of state against the background of the socio-economic and ideological conditions of the 19th century capitalist Europe (Lawith, 1964; Kaufman, 1965).

The Socio-Economic Conditions of 19th Century

Capitalism itself is simply a system of economic organization which recognized private ownership of the major means of production and propelled by profit motive, competition, self-interest and in a word, individualism. In the 19th century capitalist Europe, the socio-economic conditions were like that there was social demarcation among the people in terms of wealth, power, social inequalities in status, privileges and opportunities, and more importantly, in the control of economic, political and social resources. It was a time when the European society had already been bifurcated into two classes namely – the working class and the capitalist class. The working class served basically as elements of manipulation and exploitation in the process of capital accumulation while the emergent middle class (i.e. the capitalist class) enjoyed its glorious moments in wealth and power, and thus, wanted to consolidate its position in both economic and political scheme of things, by rationalizing with some principles and ideas be it that of liberty, reason or material progress.

Already, there was in existence, an ideology called liberalism and its economic correlate laissez faire (i.e no economic intervention by Government) which had developed in the 17th and 18th century by the efforts of the Enlightenment thinkers and classical economists of that Age-respectively. Liberalism identified the individual rather than the society as a whole as the unit of analysis upon which social justice, virtues and capabilities could be judged. Social justice was determined by the extent to which freedom was allowed the individual in order to demonstrate his own virtues and capabilities. At the economic level, this expressed itself in economic enterprise and business acumen which are themselves determined by the ingenuity of the individual which are unequally distributed by nature among men, resulting in

inequalities in wealth, status and political power (Rodee, et al, 1972 pp. 63-64). At the level of the political, the ideals of classical liberalism included:

- (i) Civil liberties – i.e. freedom of thought, expression and association
- (ii) The security of property
- (iii) The control of political institutions by an informed public opinion
- (iv) Adoption of forms of constitutional government
- (v) Acceptance of rules of government set by law
- (vi) The centre of political authority being by representative legislature
- (vii) All forms of government to be responsible to the electorate.

From the above it can be seen that the combination of economic success and the holding of political power was a function of property ownership. Earlier before this period, Aristotle had argued that the best practicable state (the polity) was that based on property ownership with the middle classes of society dominating the political system. This in itself was in opposition to Plato's own views that political leaders should have no economic stake in their political decisions and public policies, and thus should not acquire any property. But in spite of this John Calvin in the 16th century anchored political authority and justified it on the economic success of God's elect. Thus, Protestantism, and classical liberalism were fused into one in defence and protection of property rights and political power and authority.

Classical liberalism as a system of ideas concerned with the reconciliation of power and authority and the individual in a democratic setting, devoted itself to the protection of private property rights. But by the 19th century, the Natural right theory had become inadequate for rationalization and justification of property rights under capitalism, and the general atmosphere of violence therefore called the need for the production of new ideas that would be concerned with finding a non-violent and relatively non-exploitative way of carrying along the capitalist system of economic production, and winning back the obedience of the populace. It was to this need that Hegel responded to, with his political philosophy of dialectical politics and theory of state (Bosanquet, 1899; Hobhouse, 1918; Stace, 1924; Pelczynski, 1964).

The Ethical Doctrine of State

The ethical doctrine of state often referred to in the literature as dialectical theory of state like all philosophical theories was advanced by Hegel in the 19th century to address the peculiar political, social and economic problems of the German society and capitalist Europe, and to justify and rationalize the socio-political existential orders of the origin and form of the state. Hegel says, the state is the third moment of ethical life. Prior to the emergence of the state as political community, Hegel argues, that there was nothing on earth until the spirit appeared and projected for itself an order. This order developed from different stages to become a State at the third moment of ethical life (Hegel, 1921; Reyburn, 1921; Russell, 1953; Sabine and Thorson, 1973). For Hegel, the ethical life is made up of three moments namely:

- The family
- The civil society
- The State

The family as first moment of ethical life is a social institution which serves as a building block of the society. It is made up of the husband, wife and children who are bound together both biologically and emotionally. The family exists to satisfy the daily recurrent needs. Hegel divided the family into three phases namely;

- Marriage
- Family property and capital
- Family dissolution

In marriage, Hegel says it is the union of a man and woman who come together either for care which they have for one another or by the benevolent forethought of their parents. This means that under normal circumstance both parents love their children and wanted them to be together as married couples. This is done primarily by the parents, to secure the future for both children.

In the case of family property and capital, Hegel says or argues that in order for family existence to be effectual, it must be represented by property. Each family must possess and own property and such property must take the form of capital and be under the control of the husband. Every member of the family is entitled to this property which takes care of all

family responsibilities including health care and education of the children. This process overtime, leads to the final phase family dissolution.

At the phase of family dissolution in family development, the children have been educated and trained and are subsequently married out and employed into different sectors of the economy and production. This development gives rise to a new family as well as new system of needs and new economic system.

The civil society is the second moment of the ethical life according to Hegel. The civil society is a collection of small families and other social institutions that interact with one another within the system. Here again, Hegel identifies three phases or moments that make up the civil society.

These are:

- System of need
- Administration of justice
- The Police and corporation.

System of need: The moment of system of needs comes into being when the original family dissolves and a new family emerges with new economic system of exchange where people interacting in the society begin to produce what they do not need, and buy what they don't have or produce. This contradictory situation gives rise to conflict and the need to adjudicate over the problems that inevitably arise from their human conduct to one another becomes a matter of course. It is this need to adjudicate over the problems that gave rise to the second moment of the civil society i.e. the administration of justice.

The administration of justice: This process involves procedures of settling the differences and disputes arising from economic exchange and human conduct in the society. It is in this process of achieving effective settlement of disputes through the administration of justice, that the police and corporations emerge in society as the third moment of civil society.

The Police and corporation: The police and corporations as the third moment of the civil society exist because of certain inconsistencies present in the first (i.e. family) and the second (i.e civil society) moments. Ordinarily, people will not obey the law of property, hence the

police came into being in order to achieve compliance. Corporations for Hegel are simply groups like the trade unions who promote the interest of her members.

THE STATE

For Hegel, the State is the third and highest moment of ethical life. The State is an abstract and sovereign entity created by men to mediate over them. It exists to provide for the common good of all. Therefore, the State is seen as a representative of God on earth because it stands for justice and treats everyone equally which explains the ethical life. According to him, thus, the State is seen as the best moment because everyone finds satisfaction in the State. For Hegel, there are three classes that make up the State namely;

- *The fundamental class* – who are of course those involved in primary production of agricultural produce (farmers, labourers, artisans).
- *The Rational class* – those entrepreneurs who own factories and are involved in the production of factory goods and equipment.
- *The Universal class* – that is, the drivers of the State who carry out the day to day activities of the state/government. These are usually the civil servants, who provide the conducive atmosphere and environment for the other classes to actualize their potentials.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it may be said that the dialectical theory of State like all other theories of State within the philosophical tradition, such as the organic, social contractarian theory and the Marxist instrumentalist theories was a response to the socio-political problems of the 18th and 19th centuries to which Hegel lived and died. Since the crises and the contradictions of capitalist Europe of that time bordered on the extent to which labour was alienated and exploited for profit by capital, which engendered rapid changes in the society, the Hegelian dialectical theory was to discover the grounds upon which those changes were to be explained and upon which the State at its ethical moment, should exercise authority over its members whether of the capitalist or laboring classes, in order to protect them from the uncertainties, deprivations and miseries of a capitalist world immersed in a spate of violence and confusion. He had a valid problem of social disorder, dislocation and disillusionment

arising from the social differentiation among the people in terms of social dissimilarity in power, wealth, privileges and opportunities. More prominently, there was large disparity to the control the political, economic and social resources particularly wealth, prestige and respect and honours. These disparities were even made worse by the preponderance of liberalism, the political correlate of capitalism that tried to justify the existing socio-economic order. Infact, it was right and proper that Hegel, using his great intellectual might should rise to the challenge by developing a dialectical theory of State that sought to explain and justify the emergence of the State as an ethical moral entity and a basis for realizing the good life within a philosophical system of things in a rapidly changing world.

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